

Public launch of Baseline Application

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Executive summary

In this document we report about the GuestXR baseline system which is available to the public. The baseline system was developed by Virtual Bodyworks (VBW), it is an immersive shared virtual and extended reality system where participants can meet as full body avatars and talk about a topic of their choice. The architecture and system components are described in more detail in D3.1. The system is available as an AppLab app on the Meta App store and participants are invited by email. The system also requires authentication on an online system maintained by VBW to be able to deliver personalised avatars. The system offers a choice of experiences that can be selected from, which represent test spaces and prototypes of the different use cases in WP5. Human participants can be joined by the Guest system which is represented by a Python library which provides a set of preliminary actions.

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Introduction

In this document we describe the baseline application that is available to the public. The application appears on the Meta App store as an AppLab application after acceptance of an invitation email. The application is a shared virtual and augmented reality system that enables participants to share a virtual space or augmented reality space in which the participants are embodied in full body avatars and their body movements are mapped to the embodied avatars in a natural way. Participants can communicate with each other simply by talking to each other and through body movements. We briefly describe the installation and authentication functionality and then explain the different experiences available.

Through configuration we are able to specify the look of the environment and if it is a shared augmented reality or purely virtual reality experience. It can be configured to use a personalised avatar or to select from a provided choice of avatars. It also allows us to configure other possibilities of interaction, for example the Fishpond experience demonstrates a Tragedy of the Commons game in which participants can catch fish by pressing a VR UI button and they can see how the limited resource, the number of fish, is affected by their catching of fish. We also show and explain a prototype of the global warming use case experience in which participants can interact with a planet earth model through touch and they can talk with each other. Further, we give another example where participants can grasp an object and let go of it to leave the object's behaviour under control of the built in physics engine and show how gravity and collision response would move it in a natural way.

Finally, we briefly discuss the possibilities that the system currently provides for an external Guest software system to act on the environment and interact with the participants through Python commands.

1 The Application

In this document we describe the baseline system of the GuestXR project that is available to the public. The system runs on Meta Quest stand-alone systems and may also be built with minor changes on Pico Neo systems. We have tested the system on the Quest 2 and the Quest Pro stand-alone headset systems and it is expected to also work on the original Meta Quest and upcoming Meta Quest 3 devices. The system enables participants to meet in a shared virtual space embodied as full body avatars where their real body movements are mapped to their avatar's body and they can communicate by talking or through body language. The system currently works best when the participants can stand or walk around in their real spaces, where their movements in their real space are mapped to the movements of their embodied avatars. Collisions of the embodied avatars hands with virtual objects is currently translated to haptic vibrotactile feedback on the Quest controllers.

1.1 Installation

The system is available through Meta's AppLab infrastructure and after accepting an invitation the app appears as an icon in the Meta App Store. See the top right icon in Figure 1 as the current Icon to access the app. Participants can download and install the application directly from the Meta App store simply by clicking on the Icon of the app. The AppLab infrastructure also provides the possibility to update the App when a new version is deployed. Once we have deployed a new version of the app, the participants will be asked if they want to update to the latest version.

Figure 1 The VBW GuestXR system is available as an AppLab app and can be downloaded and installed from the Meta App Store directly on the Quest connected to the WIFI without the need for any additional hardware. The App appears in the Store after invitation email.

1.2 Authentication

In order for the app to be able to identify the participant, the participant has to log in to the app through the participant's credentials (see Figure 2). This is required for example to be able to deliver personalised avatars to the participant and in the future could be used to collect participant performance or body movement and voice recordings stored with the participant's account. Currently for a participant to reset his password requires getting in contact with VBW staff. We are working on adding a password reset button inside the VR experience so that once pushed, an email will be sent to the participant's account email address and the password can be reset by following the link provided in that email.

Figure 2 User authentication is accomplished in VR by providing a Keyboard UI element that enables participants to enter their account credentials, their email address and their password.

1.3 Experience Choice

Once authenticated the participant will be given a choice of experiences that are currently provided by the system. These experiences basically are configurations of the application. Through configuring it is specified which environment the experience uses, which avatars are available for embodiment and which elements there are for interactivity. Through the configuration of the environment, it is also possible to decide if an experience is an AR or a purely VR experience. This is specified through the transparency settings of the environment. If the last layer of the environment is transparent then the experience will be an AR experience. In addition, the configuration specifies which network settings are used for the participants' communication as avatars. It is therefore possible to have different network sharing rooms for each experience and therefore the possibility for each experience to be available only for those participants that have chosen that experience.

At the time of writing the system provides 3 experiences, the Fish Pond, the Planet Earth and the Object Grasping experience (see Figure 3).

Figure 3 The participant can then chose from a set of shared experiences. Currently these are the Fish Pond, Planet Earth and the Grasping Racial bias study prototype.

In addition, through configuration it is possible to specify if the experience uses a personalised avatar, if it uses a pre-defined avatar, or if it provides a choice of avatars. Figure 4 shows a choice of a set of avatars that can be provided if the experience does not configure a personalised or pre-defined avatar for embodiment.

Figure 4 If the experience is configured to provide a choice of avatars then a menu will appear where the avatars that can be chosen from are displayed.

In Figure 5 an image of the AR experience for the global warming is shown. This is still a prototype that is developed for the global warming use case in WP5. Currently the only interactivity it provides is through the interaction between the participants and through haptic feedback when the hand of the participant's embodied avatar touches the planet.

The planet is currently visualised as a sphere with a video texture from EUMETSAT¹ and NASA. The idea is that in an upcoming version there will be interactivity in the texture image visualised to display changes in the climate caused by the touch of the participants.

Figure 5 Planet Earth prototype to raise awareness of global warming and the necessity to collaborate to improve the climate situation.

Figure 6 depicts a screenshot of the AR (for reasons of capturing the parts of the pass through video feed from the real environment are shown in black) Fish Pond experience. The Fish Pond experience is another prototype for the climate change use case in which participants have the possibility to catch fish from the common pond simply by clicking a button. The shared limited resource is the number of fish in the pond which currently is visualised simply by a number. In Figure 6 the Guest external system is being tested which in this example has in addition to the 4 participants 20 agents added to test the rendering performance and the overall compute requirements of the system.

¹ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wVRbeGc_6zM

Figure 6 The Fish Pond Tragedy of the Commons game where the limited resource, the number of fish, is visualised as a number in the center.

In Figure 7 an image from the experience that enables the participant to grasp objects and to move them and also to let go of them again is shown. If the object is let go, its behaviour is taken over by the physics engine and it will collide with the table or another object and respond to the collisions in a natural way. This experience is a prototype for a user study that aims to relate motor reaching actions to racial bias. In this study participants will be embodied in a set of avatars with different skin colour representing a person from a specific race. Reaching actions will be recorded and evaluated to see if embodiment can influence the reaching behaviour. We will add a virtual mirror to this experience for the participant to be able to see the embodied avatar, in addition to the first-person perspective, also reflected in the virtual mirror.

Figure 7 In the object grasping experience the participant has the possibility to reach out and grasp an object. A prototype for a study that aims to relate reaching actions to racial bias.

1.4 Guest Actions

The external Guest system can join any of the rooms through the Python interface and by specifying the corresponding network room id. Through Python commands the Guest entity has additional capabilities as described in more detail in D3.1. For example, it can change the colour and intensity of the lights, change the appearance of each participant while embodied, by setting a different avatar. It can also add, animate, talk through and remove agents. Since the Python API also provides the possibility to get information about the agents positions a simple Python script could be written that moves agents or objects in relation to the positions of the participants. Or more complex behaviour of a Reinforcement Learning based AI system could interact by changing aspects of the environment, the avatars, adding and moving humanoid agents, etc.

2 CONCLUSIONS

We have described the baseline application that is available to the public. The application appears on the Meta App store as an AppLab application after acceptance of an invitation email. The application is a shared VR and AR system that enables participants to share a virtual space or augmented reality space where the participants are embodied in full body avatars and their body movements are mapped to the embodied avatars in a natural way. Participants can communicate with each other simply by talking to each other and through body movements. The application is highly configurable, and we showed a set of example experiences. We described the installation; the authentication and the choice of experiences and what actions are available to an external software entity that can join the experience

Overall, the system is a baseline for the GuestXR project and in active development and much functionality is being added at the time of writing.

